

The Importance of Digital Technologies in Elementary Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy Classes

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Abstract. *This article describes the importance of digital technologies in the course of the lesson, the effectiveness and useful aspects of mutual integration of subjects. It is said that connecting not only several subjects, but also topics within the subjects will be highly effective and motivate students to be interested in the lesson.*

Key words: *technology, science, education, effective lesson, method, practical, course, interest.*

Modern digital technologies provide new tools for the development of all educational institutions around the world, that is, they become the basis for modernization. Digitization creates opportunities to share lessons learned and knowledge, empowering people to be more informed and make better decisions in their daily lives. In the near future, great changes are taking place in the educational environment related to digitization.[1]

Currently, most of the educational organizations are implementing the initial form of digitization of education. This makes it possible to ease students' access to educational materials, reduce the educational load that is not of social importance, and facilitate control over the educational discipline and the content of the educational process.

Robert Carlos says that primary school should do more than just teach reading, writing and counting, but more important and bigger. Because stimulating the intellectual activity of a child during the entire formation period is very important for his future success, as well as his natural ability.

In the education system of our country, the wide use of information and communication technologies is being promoted in teaching school subjects. Information technology is a universal tool of education. Modern technologies not only form the knowledge, skills and abilities of students, but also play an important role in directing them to study, study, develop their personal characteristics and increase their interest in learning. ICT has a great influence on the expansion of students' outlook, thinking, creative qualities, theoretical knowledge and reflexive thinking. Basically, ICTs increase students' imaginative thinking and help them acquire scientific knowledge more easily and closely. The main goal of the introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process is to establish a modern education system. We know that young people are the foundation of the future. Mother tongue classes are the foundation of educational processes. Therefore, the honorable profession of teachers of native language classes requires important and responsible attention. Because, in order for students to master the education system in higher grades, they need to know basic skills, reading, writing, and calculations at a high level. Today's teacher is required to be able to use information technologies during the lesson, to teach students to acquire modern knowledge thoroughly, to become intellectually mature individuals, to use computers freely. Experiences in the use of information technologies create unlimited opportunities for individualization and

differentiation of educational processes in the case of didactically correct use of ICT in the traditional classroom. They allow to implement new forms and methods of education.

If the role of primary education is correctly understood, the student who is directed by the teacher to the correct understanding of the works in the reading book will be able to work independently, read and understand the opinions of others. learns to progress, to observe the world of feelings of himself and others, to feel others. He discovers the Universe, Man and Self. He directly participates in the formation of his inner "I". [1, 35b] There are several types of digital technologies that should be used in primary education. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the following main types of digital technologies: 1) computer program-based teaching digital technology; 2) electronic-module technology; 3) distance education technology; 4) independent education technology; 5) individual approach technology; 6) Internet education technology; 7) technology of national portals; 8) personal technology of skilled pedagogues. It is appropriate to use these types of digital technologies based on the school environment and capabilities. For example, today general secondary schools are equipped with modern computer equipment. Therefore, it is important to use the digital technology of computer-based teaching in primary education with its fun, speed and efficiency. For this, the following should be done: a) preparation of computer versions of the topics; b) creating mechanisms for presenting computer options to students and using them; c) providing students with knowledge and skills on relevant topics through virtual communication; g) presentation of prepared educational materials rich in animation and multimedia images; d) to determine the method of controlling the learning process of students. This approach allows for in-depth teaching of primary education subjects. One of the unique possibilities of digital technologies is the availability of updating educational materials.

Mastering the basic subjects and teaching intra-subject and inter-subject connections in understanding the laws of things in the world is the methodological basis of the approach to the integration of education. This can be achieved by returning many times to the concepts of the lessons, deepening and enriching them, identifying important signs that are understandable to this age. Thus, any lesson with a well-formed structure and transfer procedure, which includes a group of concepts related to this educational subject, can be used as a basis for integration. main attention is paid.

In conclusion, the specific characteristics of mother tongue and reading literacy lessons based on modern technologies can change the structures of the student's brain by helping students understand literary examples. Characters change in the process of understanding, good character and noble views are formed.

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